

News from the Magellanic Clouds

Kathy Vivas (NOIRLab), David Nidever (Montana State University, NOIRLab), & Knut Olsen (NOIRLab), on behalf of the SMASH Collaboration

Tomás Ruiz-Lara (Kapteyn Astronomical Institute, the Netherlands), Pol Massana (University of Surrey, UK), Cameron Bell (Leibniz-Institut für Astrophysik Potsdam, Germany)

The Survey of the MAgellanic Stellar History (SMASH; [1]) was designed to study in depth the two largest satellites of the Milky Way, the Magellanic Clouds. This survey, with the Dark Energy Camera (DECam; which is funded mainly by the US Department of Energy), mapped 480 square degrees (distributed over 2,400 square degrees in and around the Clouds) in five photometric bands (*ugriz*) down to magnitude ~ 24 in each band. All of the observations were released in SMASH DR2 [2] and are available via NOIRLab's Astro Data Lab. Although the observations were collected during the period 2013–2016, the SMASH collaboration continues exploiting the rich dataset. We report here three new exciting results from the survey.

Part of the SMASH dataset showing a wide-angle view of the Small Magellanic Cloud. (Credit: CTIO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/SMASH/D. Nidever (Montana State University). Image processing: T. Rector (University of Alaska Anchorage)/M. Zamani/D. de Martin)

The Stability of the Spiral Arms in the LMC

Tomás Ruiz-Lara

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of the stellar mass fractions of stars of different ages in the LMC disk (youngest to oldest from the top-left to the bottom-right panels). Note how the spiral arm is easily seen at most ages, especially those younger than 2 billion years. (From [3], with permission)

Some galaxies in the Universe display beautiful and appealing features known as spiral arms. In fact, these spiral arms are the most peculiar characteristic of the spiral galaxies, among which we find our own galaxy, the Milky Way. However, although we might be familiar with images of galaxies displaying gorgeous symmetrical arms emerging from their centers, spiral arms can manifest themselves in other ways. In fact, the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC) is the prototype of one entire family of galaxies, the Magellanic Spirals. These galaxies are characterized by the presence of barred stellar structure near their centers (the galactic bar) and one single spiral arm.

We know that galactic collisions can result in the formation of spiral patterns and that these patterns are linked to overdense regions where the formation of new stars is triggered. Nevertheless, we are still far from knowing all about these peculiar structures. How are they ultimately formed? Are they long-lasting or destroyed and reformed every now and then?

Taking advantage of the high quality of the SMASH data, Ruiz-Lara et al. [3] studied the star formation history of the entire LMC. To do so, they compared color-magnitude diagrams (CMDs) with sophisticated stellar population models to determine the locations of stars of different ages within the LMC. The result is shown in Figure 1. Stars younger than 2 billion years accumulate in the northern part of the system, coinciding with the position of the spiral arm. If star formation tends to proceed in the spiral arms, it is normal that young stars are located in the arm. However, we need to consider an important aspect here: the LMC is a dynamical system and its stars are in constant movement. Roughly speaking, it takes around 200 million years for a star to orbit around the center of the LMC, and in a couple of such orbits, everything should be well mixed.

The reported spatial coherence for stars younger than 2 billion years provides clear evidence that this structure has been in place for at least the last ~ 2 billion years. In other words, the LMC spiral arm is a stable, long-lived structure.

What happened to the LMC around 2 billion years ago? Mutual interactions between the LMC and the Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC) have long been invoked to explain large-scale structures in the Magellanic system. In particular, recent numerical studies claim that recurrent interactions between the Clouds started happening ~ 2.7 billion years ago.

If we put all the pieces of this puzzle together, a coherent scenario emerges. Around 2–3 billion years ago, there was a close approach or encounter between the LMC and the SMC that triggered the formation of a stable dynamical structure, the LMC spiral arm. This structure has been in place and forming stars for the last couple of billion years.

Exploring the Outermost Parts of the SMC

Pol Massana

The outskirts of galaxies can hold important clues to their past interactions, in particular in the form of tidal debris. The identification and characterization of such debris are crucial to our understanding of galaxy assembly, and the SMC holds an important key in trying to solve this puzzle. Being the smaller galaxy in the Magellanic Cloud pair, it is expected to lose more of its stellar content as a result of tidal stripping under the presence of the LMC, as evidenced by

its elongated shape and the existence of the Magellanic Stream.

In Massana et al. [4], we use the excellent depth of the SMASH data to analyze the structure in “island” fields in the outskirts of the SMC. We use stars in the oldest main sequence turn-off (MSTO) area of the color-magnitude diagram to trace faint structures. For the SMC, we

Figure 2. *Left*: Star count density profile of SMC MSTO stars. The points are color-coded according to the position angle of each field. The gray band shows our uncertainty in the foreground counts of the Milky Way, and the error bars for each field represent the statistical Poisson uncertainty. We highlight the position of fields 8 and 17 that show a significantly higher density than the foreground level at radii larger than the expected for the SMC. *Right*: Density map of RGB stars, with saturation at 140 counts, from [5], with the SMASH fields overlaid as red polygons. The two dashed circles represent the 4 (white) and 8 (black) degree circles around the center of the SMC. Fields 8 and 17 sit on an overdense region of Magellanic Cloud debris. (From [4], with permission)

constructed a stellar density profile that reveals its very disrupted nature. We find evidence for Magellanic Cloud debris out to a radius of ~ 12 degrees from the center of the SMC (Figure 2, left panel). This profile shows the density of Magellanic Cloud stars above the Milky Way foreground level (gray). This provides further evidence of the picture

given by *Gaia* DR2 [5], which also found a Magellanic feature in the same area (Figure 2, right panel). This is an exciting result that helps bring to the forefront the analysis of tidal structures around the Magellanic Clouds to explore their past interactions.

A New Method for Obtaining the Reddening of the SMC

Cameron Bell

The Magellanic Clouds are benchmark laboratories for studies of, among other things, star formation at lower metallicities and constraining the extragalactic distance scale (and by extension the Hubble constant). Such studies are dependent upon an understanding of the amount and spatial distribution of dust across the Magellanic Clouds. However, the issue is that the use of differently aged stellar populations to quantify the reddening in the Magellanic Clouds results in statistically significant differences.

Bell et al. [6] introduced a technique to map the intrinsic reddening of a foreground extinguishing medium using the spectral energy distributions (SEDs) of background galaxies. This technique not only removes the aforementioned stellar population dependency but also probes the total reddening by sampling the full column depth of the extinguishing medium.

Recently, Bell et al. [7] extended this technique to map the intrinsic reddening across ~ 34 deg² of the SMC. The reddening map was derived using optical (*ugriz*) and near-infrared (*YJKs*) SEDs of background galaxies that were created from the SMASH survey and the VISTA survey of the Magellanic Clouds system (VMC) data, respectively. Figure 3 shows a 20×20 arcmin² resolution reddening map of the combined SMASH-VMC footprint created from a sample of $\sim 30,000$ background galaxies with low levels of intrinsic reddening. The map reveals statistically significant enhanced levels of reddening associated with the main body of the SMC compared with regions in the outskirts [$\delta E(B-V) \sim 0.3$ mag].

A comparison with reddening maps of the SMC in the literature shows that, after correcting for differences in the volume sampled, there is good agreement between maps created using background galaxies and young stars. In

Figure 3. 20×20 arcmin² resolution reddening map of the combined SMASH-VMC footprint covering ~ 34 deg² of the SMC. This map was created using only galaxies with low levels of intrinsic reddening according to the LePhare SED-fitting routine. (From [7], with permission)

contrast, significant discrepancies are found with respect to maps created using old stars or based on longer-wavelength far-infrared dust emission that could stem from biased samples in the former and/or uncertainties in the far-infrared emissivity and optical properties of the dust grains in the latter.

References

- [1] Nidever, D. L., et al. 2017, *AJ*, 154, 199
- [2] Nidever, D. L., et al. 2020, [arXiv.org:2011.3943](https://arxiv.org/abs/2011.3943)
- [3] Ruiz-Lara, T., et al. 2020, *A&A*, 639, L3
- [4] Massana, P., et al. 2020, *MNRAS*, 498, 1034
- [5] Belokurov, V. A. & Erkal, D. 2019, *MNRAS*, 482, L9
- [6] Bell, C. P. M., et al. 2019, *MNRAS*, 489, 3200
- [7] Bell, C. P. M., et al. 2020, *MNRAS*, 499, 993